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OVERVIEW OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF IRRIGATED RICE FARMERS ADOPTING FARM TECHNOLOGY ALTERNATIVES IN SOME SELECTED STATES OF NORTH WESTERN NIGERIA

BY

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ABSTRACT

Rice has been growing in importance globally due to its pervasive use and utility. This study examined the socio-economic characteristics of irrigated rice farmers adopting farm technology alternatives in some selected north western of Nigeria. The study applied cross sectional data collected among 571 irrigated rice farmers in the study areas. Structured questionnaires were used and administered on multistage sampling procedure to collect the data used in the study. Descriptive statistics particularly table, mean and standard deviation were used for data analysis. The findings of the study revealed that the mean age of adopters is higher than that of non-adopters; the mean level of education for adopters of farm technology alternatives were between tertiary institution and post-graduate studies. Also, the mean gender for adopters of farm technology alternatives was up to 89% male. Moreover, the mean marital status for adopters for farm technology alternatives was up to 99% married. Additionally, the mean household size for adopters of farm technology alternatives was dominantly below 10 persons. Lastly, the mean market distance from house for adopters of farm technology alternatives was dominantly ranging from 3 to 8 kilometers. Based on the outcome of the findings the study recommended for the need for the government to intensify campaigns on limiting family size of irrigated rice farmers in order to avoid tendency of large families denying technology adoption practices.

Key Words: Adopting Farm Technology Alternatives, Higher Yielding Varieties, Irrigated Rice Farmers, Mobile phone, Socio-economic Characteristics, and Tractor service.

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INTRODUCTION

Rice belongs to the Order *Poales* and the grass family known as *Poaceae* which was initially called *Gramineae* (Mohammed, Ibrahim, Hayatu, & Mohammed, 2019). *Oryza Sativa Indica* which originated from India and *Oryza Sativa Japonica* which originated from China are the two dominant varieties occupying the global rice farming (Friday, 2022). Rice has been growing in importance globally due to its pervasive use and utility. The increasing global demand for rice and declining availability of farm labour have made farm technologies essential. Insufficient rice production, shift in consumer preferences towards rice consumption, and a rapidly increasing population have led to high global demand for rice. Also, the growing urban sector as well as the rural non-farm economy are the driving forces for the continuous decrease in the farm labour supply on the other hand, and necessitated for the urgent need for the technology (Sarkar & Gosh, 2013; Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development [OECD], 2001).

More than half of the world's population today relies on rice as a main supplier of food energy and if not because all economic resources are naturally scarce, the volume of rice supply should have been large enough to cater for the world rising demand (Growth and Employment in States 4 [GEMS4], 2019a). Global rice production has increased by about 55 million metric tonnes since 2008 and Asian countries particularly China, India, Thailand and Srilanka are the giant producers with China (148.99 million) and India (129.47 million) alone producing 50% of the entire rice grown and consumed globally (Shahbandeh, 2023). Since the mid-1960s, world rice production has collectively risen by roughly about 1 million ton per year and it is likely that an additional 34 million metric tonnes in production per year will be needed by 2030 to meet up rice rising demand of the world expanding population (Nasrin, Lodin, Jirström, Holmquist, Djurfeldt, & Djurfeldt, 2015).

Rice production in Nigeria started with a low yielding local variety called *Oryza Glaberrima Stued* around 1500 BC that spread all the Niger delta areas (Imolehin & Wada, 2000). White grain both *Indica* and *Japonica*, *Oryza Sativa* was introduced to Nigeria around 1890 but by 1960, it accounted for 60% of the entire rice planted and consumed in the nation (Imolehin & Wada, 2000). The trends of global and national rice output from 2010 to 2022 showed unstable growth rates with two point declines between 2014 to 2015, and 2021 to 2022 for global production, while that of Nigeria indicated 3 points declines during the periods of 2012 to 2013, 2016 to 2017, and 2019 to 2020 (Shahbandeh, 2023; Sasu, 2023). Additionally, the description of Nigeria as the giant of Africa holds true, particularly regarding its rice production. Nigeria is currently the leading rice supplier in the whole of Africa with more than annual production of 8 million metric tonnes which represents 55% of the entire 14.6 million metric tonnes produced by the continent in 2019 (Olowo, 2020). Nigeria is also the 14th largest rice producer in the world after overtaking Egypt since 2017 (Olowo, 2020). Rice in Nigeria can be planted in almost all the agro-ecological areas of the nation with greatest production in the Northern part of the country (Growth and Employment in States Number 4 [GEMS4], 2019b). However, due to the fast

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growing population and the expansion in consumers' choice in favour of rice, production of rice fails to meet its rising domestic demand (Egbodion & Ahmadu, 2015).

Rice production in Nigeria is carried-out in 29 states of the federation. As of 2022, eight leading rice producing states contributed up to 50% of the entire rice produced during the year (Accret, 2023). The leading rice producing states in 2022 includes Kebbi State (3.5 million metric tonnes); Jigawa State (2.1 million metric tonnes); Kano State (1.6 million metric tonnes); each of Benue State, Ekiti State and Ebonyi State (1.5 million metric tonnes); Kaduna State (634,410 metric tonnes) and Niger State (380,000 metric tonnes). In Nigeria 910,210 hectares are currently utilized for the irrigated rice production with a total of 27 active and functioning dams of irrigating more than 550,000 hectares of land for rice farming (Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development [FMARD], 2020). Besides the prolong drought of 1970 to 1975, climatic instability particularly severe temperature, unstable rainfall season, regular flooding, as well as salty water supply are the main factors for considering irrigation as a farming option (Joshua, Ajiboye & Rashid. 2010).

Also, different administrations in Nigeria since independence implemented several programmes with the intention to achieve food self-sufficiency since 1960s (Anyanwu, Oyefusi, Oaikhenan & Dimowo, 1997). The latest include but not limited to National Rice Development Strategy I, National Rice Development Strategy II, R-I-C-E Approach, and Agricultural initiative and Development Strategy, Presidential Initiative on Rice, Agricultural Promotion Policy, Green Alternative, Anchor Brower Programme, along with Transforming Irrigation Management in Nigeria [TRIMING] were all put in place in order to establish an enabling environment for food self-sufficiency (FMARD, 2020).

North Western Nigeria is among the six geopolitical areas of the nation which represents geographical and political parts that make up the northwest (Accret, 2023). North Western States dominantly fall under the irrigation ecology that has proved to be most efficient with 3.5 average yields yearly (Ezedinma, 2019). In 2022, giant rice producing states in the sub-region like Kebbi State alone produced 3.5 million metric tonnes; Jigawa produced 2.1 million metric tonnes while Kano produced 1.5 million metric tonnes (Accret, 2023). Rice farming in the region in particular is dominated by smallholder farmers who are conservative to modernization and rely on the use of traditional technology that made them unable to harness their production potentials fully (Kamai, Omoigui, Kamara & Ekeleme, 2020). The farming areas in the North Western Nigeria are both lowland and upland. While the lowland areas are flooded Fadamas mainly for irrigation purpose characterized by 4.5 to 5 months water availability yearly, the upland areas are endowed with good soil fertility and over 700mm rainfall availability (Kamai, Omoigui, Kamara & Ekeleme, 2020).

Though Nigeria has all the potentialities to achieve self-sufficiency in rice production looking at large arable land and number of farmers, availability of Higher Yielding Variety Seeds, Tractor service, information and technology devices, designed programmes and policies and soil fertility, self-sufficiency in rice production is yet to be attained (Mohammed, Ibrahim, Hayatu & Mohammed, 2019). Consequently, huge amount of money is spent yearly by various governments in Nigeria in order to close the domestic rice supply deficit. Against the backdrop,

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this study intends to look at the socio-economic characteristics of irrigated rice farmers in three selected north western Nigerian states with a view to highlight the potentials of the farmers.

OVERVIEW OF RICE PRODUCTION IN NIGERIA

Rice is becoming more relevant crop in Nigeria. It is produced for both consumption and commercial purposes. Rice has been grown and consumed for long time in some location, but for most others, it is valued for occasional reasons (Ogundele & Okuruwa, 2006). With its more accessibility, rice has become a necessity or everyday diet among many Nigerians today. Rice farming in Nigeria started around 1500 BC with the low-yielding indigenous red grain species *Oryza glaberrima* (Stued) that was widely grown in the Niger Delta area (Rodernburg, Diagne, Oikeh, & Keya, 2014; Ogundele & Okoruwa, 2006). The high-yielding white grain, *Oryza sativa* L. was introduced around 1890 and by 1960 accounted for more than 60% of the rice grown in the country (Ogundele & Okuruwa, 2006).

Today three varieties are grown in Nigeria among which are the African rice i.e. *Oryza glaberrima*, Asian rice i.e. *Oryza sativa* and the recently WARDA's hybrid rice, NERICA available only to farmers under WARDA's PVS programme (Langtau, 2003). According to Jones (1995 cited in Langtau, 2003), the African rice *Oryza glaberrima* came from the undomesticated rice *Oryza barthii* some 3500 years ago and its progeny, domesticated around the inland delta area of the Niger from where it spread through the upper Niger valley to the rest of West Africa. African rice is cultivated both as a field crop and a paddy crop. Langtau (2003) posited that for the Niger-Benue trough, Sokoto-Rima and Chad Basin rice has been in cultivation long enough for a rice culture to have evolved going as far back as 1500 BC.

The major type of rice farmed in Nigeria is the Asian rice *Oryza sativa* (Rodernburg et al., 2014; Langtau, 2003). It is grown in almost all the agro-ecological zones in Nigeria (Akintayo & Lawal, 2010). This production is on a relatively small scale. Irrigated lowland accounts for 10 to 15 at most 27 percent of national rice production, with estimated national area share of 17% and average yield of 3.5 per hectare (Ezedinma, 2019).

Table 1: The Trend in Rice Production in Nigeria (2000-2022)

Year	Rice Production (1,000 MT)	Production Growth Rate
2000	1,979	00.66
2001	1,651	-16.57
2002	1,757	06.42
2003	1,870	06.43
2004	2,000	06.95
2005	2,140	07.00
2006	2,546	18.97
2007	2,008	-21.13

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2008	2,632	31.08
2009	2,234	-15.12
2010	2,818	26.14
2011	2,906	03.12
2012	3,423	17.79
2013	3,038	-11.25
2014	3,782	24.49
2015	3,941	04.20
2016	4,536	15.10
2017	4,470	-01.46
2018	5,249	17.43
2019	5,314	01.24
2020	5,148	-03.12
2021	5,255	02.08
2022	5,355	01.10

Source: Adopted from Sasu (2023).

- **Irrigated Farming**

Modernization made irrigation one of the farming options that can help farmers to increase output and gains by engaging in year-round farming activities. Proper irrigation is important for reliable crops growth and costs' production. According to Aiyedun (1991), irrigated farming has to do with supply of water by farmers in order to grow crops and postures. This definition tries to link irrigation with water supply which the most important aspect of this farming. Its main area of difference is regarding the supply of water by the farmers only. The major weakness of this definition is its inability to identify the sources of irrigation farming. To Sarkar and Gosh (2013), irrigated farming has to do with application of water to plants in order meet up their water requirement artificially. This definition related irrigation with water use which is the most important aspect of irrigation. The ability of the definition to use 'water requirement' qualifies it to be different. The major weakness of this definition is its inability to identify the irrigation sources.

Similarly, Tashikalma and Ugbehe (2014) defined irrigated farming as a farming of crops by application of water at intervals. This definition related the irrigation farming with application of water which the central in the definition. This definition is also different by mentioning that water application will be on interval basis. The major deficiency of this definition is its inability to identify the irrigation sources and mentioning of 'application of water at interval' cannot inform readers the length of the interval. In another perception, Ugalahi, Adeoye and Agbonlahor (2016) defined irrigated farming as an artificial way of providing cropping soil with required

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water in order to perform cultivation through tubes, pumps, and sprays. This definition also related the irrigation farming with watering cropping soil. The difference between this definition and other standard is its ability to identify some of the irrigation sources and mentioning of 'required water' which is more quantifiable than the term 'application of water at interval' used by Tashikalma and Ugbehe (2014).

This study therefore intends to look at the socio-economic characteristics of irrigated rice farmers in three selected north western Nigerian states with a view to highlight the potentials of the farmers.

METHODOLOGY

- **Description of the Study Area**

North Western Nigeria is among the six geopolitical areas of the nation which represents geographical and political parts that make up the northwest (Accret, 2023). The North West is the largest sub-region/zone in the country, making up about 59% of the entire landmass of Nigeria (Almu, Adesina & Kanmodi, 2019). It is located on Latitude $8^{\circ}14'60''N$ to $14^{\circ}30'0''N$ and Longitude $3^{\circ}30'0''E$ to $10^{\circ}24'0''E$. The sub-region had a different administrative structure before the colonization of the country and was blessed with natural resources such as cotton, groundnut, crude oil, tin, etc. Therefore, it is a major ground for agriculture, with good tourist attraction sites and special traditional delicacies. Also, Goronyo Dam of Sokoto State generated from Rima River with an area surface of 20,000 hectares for irrigation supply, Jibiya Dam of Katsina State was generated from the Gada River with an area surface of 4,000 hectares for irrigation and water supply, and the Zobe Dam of Katsina State generated from Karaduwa River with an area surface of 8,000 hectares for irrigation and hydroelectric power generation purpose (Isaac, 2021; Bosola, 2020). The cultivated areas in North Western Nigeria are lowland and upland physically characterized according to the agricultural site comprising of Aridisols in dry land sites and Vertisols in Fadama sites (USDA, 1975). The lowland areas with flooded Fadamas mainly for irrigation purposes are characterized by 4.5 to 5 months of water availability yearly while upland areas are endowed with good soil fertility and over 700mm rainfall availability (Kamai, et al., 2020).

North West lies in the Sub-Saharan Sudan belt of the West Africa in zone of Savannah-type vegetation. Rainfall averaging about 30 inches annually occurs chiefly in a wet season which lasts from May to October, with a prolonged dry season extending from October to April usually dominated by dusty harmattan winds from the Northeast (USGS, 1973). Moreover, rice production in the North western part is dominated by rainfed farming (GEMS4, 2019b). The report further revealed that as of 2016, Kano State devoted 724,502 hectares to rice production with 69% to rainfed farming only 31% went to irrigation. Jigawa State devoted 330,812 hectares with 94% rainfed and only 6% for irrigation. A total of 328,585 hectares were devoted to rice farming in Kaduna State, out of which 87% went to rainfed with only 13% into irrigation (GEMS4, 2019b). Figure 2 below describes the major rice producing states in Nigeria:

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Figure 1: North Western Rice Producing State in Nigeria

- **Research Design**

This study is cross sectional survey that focuses on the responses of irrigated rice farmers in selected states of North Western Nigeria with regard to their socio-economic characteristics using a self-designed questionnaire that were administered with the help of of trained assistants through multi-stage sampling procedure and analysed through descriptive statistics.

- **Population and Sample of the Study**

The population of the study comprises all registered irrigated rice farmers from 3 states of North Western Nigeria covered by this study. Therefore, this study covered a total of 542,206 male and female irrigated rice farmers from Kaduna, Jigawa and Kano States who are between 18 to 90 years of age. The population of farmers in Kano was obtained from the RIFAN office, Kano State and those of Kaduna and Jigawa States were obtained from some available documents in Hadeja Jama’are River Basin Development Authority, Kano. Also, the sample size for this study was determined using the formula developed by Yamane (1967). Thus;

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} \dots \dots \dots (3.1)$$

Where;

n = The sample size to be determined;

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N = Total number of units in the population i.e. sample frame of Irrigated Rice Farmers (492,206); and

e = The error margin i.e. 5% (0.05).

$$\text{Hence, } n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} = \frac{859,561}{1+859,561(0.05)^2} = 400$$

Additionally, non-response error/bias is taken care of using the formula of Fox, Hunn and Mathers (2009), who suggested dividing the earlier sample size by the response rate of respondents for better representative sample elements. Thus;

$$n_2 = \frac{n}{\omega} \dots \dots \dots (3.2)$$

Where;

n_2 = New sample size.

n = Sample size determined earlier using Yamane (1967) i.e. 400

ω = Expected response rate i.e. 70% (0.7).

$$\therefore n_2 = \frac{400}{0.7} = 571 \text{Irrigated Rice Farmers.}$$

Moreover, a sample size of each rice enumeration cluster will follow the Factor Proportion as adopted in the work of Abdullahi and Tijani (2012). Thus;

$$PF = \frac{n_3}{N_3} * 571 \dots \dots \dots (3.3)$$

Where;

PF = Number of the Irrigated Rice Farmers to be selected in each cluster.

n_3 = Total number of the i^{th} Irrigated Rice Farmers in each cluster.

N_3 = The sum of the Irrigated Rice Farmers in all the three (3) clusters selected.

571 = The desired number of Irrigated Rice Farmers suggested as the sample size through the formulae.

Regarding the sampling technique, multi-stage sampling was used to select the Irrigated Rice Farmers across the study areas. In the first stage, the seven rice-producing states were stratified into high, medium and low size of land masses from which Kaduna (high); Jigawa (medium) and Kano (low) were selected. In the second stage, to provide equal opportunity to larger and smaller

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rice-producing local governments, the local governments were stratified based on the number of Irrigated Rice Farmers-classified as high, medium and low. Therefore, Makarfi, Ringim and Kura (high); Soba, Hadejia and Doguwa (medium) and Kudan, Gwiwa and Bunkure (low) were chosen from Kaduna, Jigawa and Kano States respectively. In the third stage, villages or clusters within each selected local government area were enumerated systematically, starting with a common random start of 1 across the local governments. Skip intervals of 3, 5 and 3 were then applied for Kaduna, Jigawa and Kano respectively. Therefore, Makarfi, Soba and Hunkuyi were selected from Makarfi, Soba and Kudan Local Governments of Kaduna State; Gujaba, S/Garu and Wailare were selected from Ringim, Hadejia and Gwiwa Local Governments of Jigawa State; and Kura and Bagau, Doka Sati and Zangon Buhari were selected from Kura, Doguwa and Bunkure Local Governments of Kano State. Finally, in the fourth stage, a sampling of 571 individual Irrigated Rice Farmers was selected from the list of enumerated villages based on the availability of farmers in each village as described by Obayelu et al. (2017). The distribution of the sample farmers shown in Table 2 below:

Table 2: Distribution of the Research Sample Irrigated Rice Farmers

S/N	Name of Strata	Local Government	Selected Villages (Clusters)		Number of Respondents
			Tech. Adopters	Tech. Non-Adopters	
1	Kaduna	Makarfi L.G.A.	Makarfi (68)	Makarfi (11)	79
		Soba L.G.A.	Soba (45)	Soba (10)	55
		Kudan L.G.A.	Hunkuyi (75)	Hunkuyi (15)	90
		Sub-total			224
2	Jigawa	Ringim L.G.A.	Gujaba (39)	Gujaba (9)	48
		Hadejia L.G.A.	Sabon Garu (47)	Sabon Garu (10)	57
		Gwiwa L.G.A.	Wailare (10)	Wailare (7)	17
		Sub-total			122
3	Kano	Kura L.G.A.	Kura (80)	Kura (20)	105
			Bagau (12)	Bagau (2)	14
		Doguwa L.G.A.	Doka Sati (47)	Doka Sati (8)	55

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	Bunkure L.G.A.	Z/Buhari (45)	Z/Buhari (6)	51
Sub-total				225
4 Grand Total				571

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2024.

Note: Figure in parenthesis represents the number of sampled Irrigated Rice Farmers

- **Techniques of Data Analysis**

This study utilized descriptive statistics as a sole technique of data analysis. According to Fox, Hunn and Mathers (2009) “descriptive statistics serve a useful purpose by summarizing all data in the sum of few sample numerical expressions”. In this study, descriptive statistics tools particularly tables, mean, standard deviations and percentages were used to describe the socio-economic characteristics of the irrigated rice farmers across the areas of the study which is fundamental for any survey study. It was also used to present description and correlation of variables and reporting of all results estimate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- **Distribution and Response Rate of Questionnaire of Respondents**

This involves all the processes covering the delivery and retrieval of questionnaire instrument from the administered sampled respondents. In this study, questionnaire distribution was performed face-to-face through intervention of research assistants in each of the states where the study was conducted. Response rate means the percentage of respondents who completed and returned the questionnaire which were calculated as:

$$\frac{\text{Number of responses}}{\text{Number of questionnaire}} * 100$$

Table 3: Distribution and Response Rate of Questionnaire

S/N	Questionnaire Details	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Total Questionnaire Administered	571	100
2	Total Questionnaire Retrieved	568	98
3	Total Unreturned Questionnaire	3	1
3	Total Questionnaire Deleted	4	1
4	Total Usable Questionnaire	564	98

Source: Researcher Work, 2024.

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Table 3 reports the questionnaire administrated among the respondents Irrigated Rice Farmers and its response rate. From the table, it can be seen that the questionnaire distributed were 571, out of which 568 copies constituting 98% were successfully returned. Only 3 copies of the questionnaire, constituting 1 percent of the questionnaire given out to the respondents were not returned. Subsequently, based on Mahalanobis distance (D^2), outliers were detected resulting to a deletion of 4 copies of the questionnaire retrieved which constitutes only 1 percent of the entire retrieved questionnaire. The balance of 464 copies of the retrieved questionnaire, which constitutes 99% of the retrieved questionnaire were deemed to be usable for this analysis.

- **Consistency and Reliability Test of the Research Instrument**

This is a statistical measure of internal consistency reliability, used to evaluate the reliability of a questionnaire instrument, survey or test. The index measures how well a set of items (questions or statements) measures a single, underlying construct or concept. It ranges from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating greater internal consistency.

Table 4: Cronbach’s Alpha Reliability Index

S/N	Item	Cronbach’s alpha Index
1	Average Interitem Correlation (AIC)	0.1219
2	Number of Items in the Scale	26
3	Scale Reliability Coefficient (SRC)	0.7831

Source: Stata 14 Estimation, 2024.

Table 4 reports the reliability analysis results of 26 question items. The reliability analysis yielded a Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of 0.7831 indicating a strong and positive interitem correlation (AIC) and higher level of internal consistency among the items in the instrument. This is suggesting that the items are homogenous to measure the same underlying construct; the scale is reliable and can be used with greater confidence to measure the intended construct (supporting scale’s reliability and validity).

- **Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents**

These are the demographic and economic attributes of the individual irrigated rice farmers who participated in this survey. Table 4 reports the descriptive results of socio-economic characteristics of the irrigated rice farmers for the seven (7) adoption alternatives, the non-adoption of the and the whole sample. In this study, the mean value for the non-adoption of the ($H_0T_0M_0$) is used as a reference (base) category for comparison with the mean values of the adoption of alternatives, where ($H_1T_0M_0$) is for the adoption of Higher Yielding Varieties [HYVs] only, ($H_0T_1M_0$) is for the adoption of tractor service only, ($H_0T_0M_1$) is for the adoption

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of mobile phone only, ($H_1T_1M_0$) is for the combined adoption of HYVs and tractor service, ($H_1T_0M_1$) is for the combined adoption of HYVs and mobile phone, ($H_0T_1M_1$) is for the combined adoption of tractor service and mobile phone, and ($H_1T_1M_1$) is for the combined adoption of HYVs, tractor service and mobile phone.

Table 5: Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents

Variables	Adoption of Farm technology Alternatives							Non-Adopters	Total Sample
	$H_1T_0M_0$ (1)	$H_0T_1M_0$ (2)	$H_0T_0M_1$ (3)	$H_1T_1M_0$ (4)	$H_1T_0M_1$ (5)	$H_0T_1M_1$ (6)	$H_1T_1M_1$ (7)	$H_0T_0M_0$ (0)	
Mean	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)
AGE	42.78 (11.32)	43.02 (14.28)	34.64 (8.22)	34.21 (11.10)	43.91 (10.38)	40.78 (10.63)	37.39 (12.47)	29.39 (6.21)	37.94 (11.84)
EDU	3.29 (0.92)	3.33 (0.63)	2.78 (0.80)	1.95 (1.11)	3.38 (1.02)	3.55 (0.75)	3.32 (0.71)	1.88 (1.10)	2.90 (1.06)
GEN	0.89 (0.32)	0.93 (0.25)	0.90 (0.31)	0.79 (0.41)	0.91 (0.29)	0.83 (0.38)	0.80 (0.41)	0.77 (0.43)	0.86 (0.35)
MARS	0.99 (0.14)	0.98 (0.14)	0.87 (0.34)	1.00 (0.00)	1.00 (0.00)	0.90 (0.30)	0.77 (0.42)	0.79 (0.41)	0.91 (0.29)
HSZ	4.68 (0.64)	12.06 (0.64)	9.77 (1.68)	3.21 (1.98)	6.06 (1.62)	4.98 (0.36)	3.61 (0.56)	10.76 (1.06)	7.97 (1.52)
DIST	7.29 (2.89)	7.70 (1.39)	5.17 (1.71)	2.53 (1.56)	2.59 (1.73)	8.35 (2.12)	4.86 (0.74)	3.43 (0.41)	5.60 (1.29)
Sample Farmers	n=105 (18.62%)	n=102 (18.09%)	n=107 (18.97)	n=34 (6.03%)	n=34 (6.03%)	n=40 (7.09%)	n=44 (7.80%)	n=98 (17.36%)	n=564

Source: Researcher's Estimation Using Stata 14, 2024.

%=Percentage in Parenthesis.

Note: n represents the size of sub samples for different farm technology alternatives' adopters, non-adopters ($H_0T_0M_0$) and the total sample.

From the results of socio-economic characteristics of Irrigated Rice Farmers as reported in Table 5, showed some level of heterogeneity between adopters and non-adopters as well as across the adopters of the available Farm technology alternatives.

- **Age of Respondents**

The mean age of the non-adopters of farm technology is about 29 years, that of adopters of alternative 1(adoption of HYVs only) and 2(adoption of Tractor service only) are 43 years each, that of adopters of alternative 3(adoption of Mobile phone only), 4(combined adoption of HYVs & Tractor service), 5(combined adoption of HYVs & Mobile phone), 6(combined adoption of Tractor service & Mobile phone) and 7(combined adoption of HYVs, Tractor service & Mobile

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phone) are about 35, 34, 44, 41 and 38 years respectively. The mean age difference shows that adopters of the 7 Farm technology alternatives have statistical and significant higher age than non-adopters of the Farm technology all at 1% level. This implies that the age of the adopters of Farm technology alternatives are statistically and significantly higher than that of non-adopters. Therefore, Irrigated Rice Farmers with higher age are better experienced and more likely to adopt the available Farm technology alternatives.

- **Education Level of Respondents**

The mean level of education for non-adopters of the Farm technology is about 2 years, that of adopters of alternative 1(adoption of HYVs only), 2(adoption of Tractor service only), 3(adoption of Mobile phone only), 5(combined adoption of HYVs & Mobile phone) and 7(combined adoption of HYVs, Tractor service & Mobile phone) are about 3 years each, that of adopters of alternative 4(combined adoption of HYVs & Tractor service) and 6(combined adoption of Tractor service & Mobile phone) are about 2 and 4 years respectively. The mean level of education difference shows that adopters of alternative 1(adoption of HYVs only), 2(adoption of Tractor service only), 3(adoption of Mobile phone only), 5(combined adoption of HYVs & Mobile phone), 6(combined adoption of Tractor service & Mobile phone) and 7(combined adoption of HYVs, Tractor service & Mobile phone) have statistical and significant higher level of education than non-adopters of the Farm technology at 1% level, only adopters of alternative 4(combined adoption of HYVs & Tractor service) has statistical and significant equal or similar level of education with non-adopters of the Farm technology at 1% level too. This implies that level of education of the adopters of Farm technology alternatives with exception of combined adopters of HYVs and Tractor service, are statistically and significantly higher than that of non-adopters. Therefore, Irrigated Rice Farmers with higher years of formal education (possessing Secondary levels or higher) are more literate and likely to adopt the available Farm technology alternatives.

- **Gender of Respondents**

The majority of the non-adopters of Farm technology were identified as male (77%, n=75), with the remaining (23%, n=23) identified as female. The majority of Farm technology adopters for alternative 1(adoption of HYVs only), 2(adoption of Tractor service only), 3(adoption of Mobile phone only), 4(combined adoption of HYVs & Tractor service), 5(combined adoption of HYVs & Mobile phone), 6(combined adoption of Tractor service & Mobile phone) and 7(combined adoption of HYVs, Tractor service & Mobile phone) were identified as male (89%, n=93; 93%, n=95; 90%, n=96; 79%, n=27; 91%, n=31; 82%, n=33 and 80%, n=35) respectively, with the remaining (11%, n=12; 7%, n=7; 10%, n=11; 21%, n=7; 9%, n=3; 18%, n=7 & 20%, n=9) identified as female. The mean gender difference shows that adopters of alternative 1(adoption of HYVs only), 3(adoption of Mobile phone only) and 7(combined adoption of HYVs, Tractor service & Mobile phone) have statistical and significant higher male majority than non-adopters each at 1% level, that of adopters of alternative 2(adoption of Tractor service only), 4(combined adoption of HYVs & Tractor service) and 6(combined adoption of Tractor service & Mobile phone) have statistical and significant higher male majority than non-adopters each at 5% level.

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The mean gender difference shows that only adopters of alternative 5(combined adoption of HYVs & Mobile phone) has statistical and significant higher male majority than non-adopters at 10% level. This implies that the proportions of male gender are higher among adopters of the Farm technology. Therefore, Irrigated Rice Farmers that are dominantly male more likely to adopt the available Farm technology.

- **Marital Status of Respondents**

The majority of the non-adopters of Farm technology were identified as married (79%, n=77), with the remaining (21%, n=21) identified as single. The whole adopters of the Farm technology alternative 4(combined adoption of HYVs & Tractor service) and 5(combined adoption of HYVs & Mobile phone) were identified as married. The majority of Farm technology adopters for alternative 1(adoption of HYVs only), 2(adoption of Tractor service only), 3(adoption of Mobile phone only), 6(combined adoption of Tractor service & Mobile phone) and 7(combined adoption of HYVs, Tractor service & Mobile phone) were identified as married (99%, n=104; 98%, n=100; 87%, n=93; 90%, n=36 and 77%, n=34) respectively, with the remaining (1%, n=1; 2%, n=2; 13%, n=14; 10%, n=4 & 23%, n=10) identified as single. The mean marital status difference shows that adopters of alternative 3(adoption of Mobile phone only), 4(combined adoption of HYVs & Tractor service), 5(combined adoption of HYVs & Mobile phone) and 7(combined adoption of HYVs, Tractor service & Mobile phone) have statistical and significant higher marital majority than non-adopters each at 1% level, that of adopters of alternative 6(combined adoption of Tractor service & Mobile phone) has statistical and significant higher male majority than non-adopters only at 10% level. The mean marital status difference between the adopters of alternative 1(adoption of HYVs only) and 2(adoption of Tractor service only) and that of non-adopters is statistically and significantly the same. This implies that the proportions of married adopters of Farm technology are higher among the adopters of alternative 3(adoption of Mobile phone only), 4(combined adoption of HYVs & Tractor service), 5(combined adoption of HYVs & Mobile phone), 6(combined adoption of Tractor service & Mobile phone) and 7(combined adoption of HYVs, Tractor service & Mobile phone) the Farm technology. Therefore, Irrigated Rice Farmers that are dominantly married more likely to adopt the available Farm technology.

- **Household Size of Respondents**

The mean household size of non-adopters of the Farm technology is about 11 persons, that of adopters of alternative 1(adoption of HYVs only), 2(adoption of Tractor service only), 3(adoption of Mobile phone), 4(combined adoption of HYVs & Tractor service), 5(combined adoption of HYVs & Mobile phone), 6(combined adoption of Tractor service and Mobile phone) and 7(combined adoption of HYVs, Tractor service & Mobile phone) are 5, 12, 10, 3, 6, 5 and 4 persons respectively. The mean household size difference shows that only adopters of alternative 2(adoption of Tractor service only) have statistical and significant higher household size than non-adopters of the Farm technology at 1% level, that of adopters of alternative 1(adoption of HYVs only), 3(adoption of Mobile phone), 4(combined adoption of HYVs & Tractor service), 5(combined adoption of HYVs & Mobile phone), 6(combined adoption of Tractor service and Mobile phone) and 7(combined adoption of HYVs, Tractor service & Mobile phone) have

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statistical and significant lower household size than non-adopters of the Farm technology at 1% level too. This implies that adopters of the Farm technology dominantly possess smaller number of family size. Therefore, Irrigated Rice Farmers with small household size are more likely to adopt the available Farm technology in order to achieve higher farm performance.

- **Market Distance of Respondents**

The mean distance to market from house for non-adopters of Farm technology is about 3 kilometers, that of adopters of alternative 1(adoption of HYVs only) is 7 kilometers, that of alternative 3(adoption of Mobile phone) and 7(combined adoption of HYVs, Tractor service & Mobile phone) are 5 kilometers each. The mean distance to market for the adopters of alternative 2(adoption of Tractor service) and 6(combined adoption of Tractor service and Mobile phone) are 8 kilometers each, that of adopters of alternative 4(combined adoption of HYVs & Tractor service) and 5(combined adoption of HYVs & Mobile phone) are 3 kilometers each. The mean distance to market difference shows that adopters of alternative 1(adoption of HYVs only) has statistical and significant higher distance to market than non-adopters of the Farm technology at only 10% level, that of adopters of alternative 2(adoption of Tractor service), 3(adoption of Mobile phone) and 7(combined adoption of HYVs, Tractor service & Mobile phone) have statistical and significant higher distance to market than non-adopters of the Farm technology at 1% levels. The mean distance to market difference shows that adopters of alternative 4(combined adoption of HYVs & Tractor service) and 5(combined adoption of HYVs & Mobile phone) and non-adopters are statistically and significantly equal. This implies that adopters of the alternative Farm technology possess relative higher distance to the market than non-adopters counterparts. Therefore, Irrigated Rice Farmers that are in relatively longer distance are more likely adopt the available Farm technology.

CONCLUSION

From the outcome of this study, the mean age for non-adopters of farm technology was 29 years at most. Those of adopters of farm technology alternatives were at 30s and 40s years of age. This implies those adopters for farm technology alternative is relatively higher. The mean level of education for non-adopters of farm technology alternatives was secondary level. Those of adopters of farm technology alternatives were between tertiary institution and post-graduate studies. The mean gender for non-adopters of farm technology alternatives was 77% males with only 23% female. That of adopters of farm technology alternatives was up to 89% male with only 1 per cent female.

The mean percentage of marital status for non-adopters for farm technology alternatives was 79% married. That of adopters for farm technology alternatives was up to 99% married. The mean household size of non-adopters for farm technology alternatives was 11 persons. That of adopters for farm technology alternatives was dominantly below 10 persons. Lastly, the mean market distance of non-adopters for farm technology was only 3 kilometers. That of adopters for farm technology alternatives was dominantly ranging from 3 to 8 kilometers.

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• Recommendations

Based on the conclusions presented above, the following recommendations were offered:

- i. There is need for the government to improve the level of education among irrigation rice farmers in the study areas in order to promote their potentials toward technology adoption through establishment of distance learning centers.
- ii. There is need for the government to intensify campaigns on limiting family size of irrigated rice farmers in order to avoid tendency of large families denying technology adoption practices through effective public enlightenments.

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